

PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF FORMATION OF LEARNING
MOTIVATION IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS.

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Abstract: Formation of higher knowledge, skills and qualifications in primary grades activities aimed at increasing the effectiveness of educational activities for It is also important to study the issues of students' motivations becomes important. This article provides information about the psychological factors of the formation of learning motivation in elementary school students.

Key words: primary education, learning situations, pedagogical-psychological features, subject, individual directed education.

Today, many problems of modern education are relevant, mainly manifested in the child himself, his behavior and educational activities. One of them is the formation of educational motivation in schoolchildren. The modern conditions of the development of the society set priority directions and tasks for the basic school education system, and require the search for ways to significantly increase its quality. However, in organizing the educational process, school administrators and teachers face a number of difficulties, one of which is the low educational motivation of students. Nevertheless, in the history of pedagogy and psychology, certain experiences have been collected in the field under consideration, their analysis and theoretical understanding will help to solve the identified problem. Cognitive activity is one of the leading forms of child activity, which stimulates learning through cognitive interest.

Learning gives the student confidence in his actions. It's up to the student to know cooperative education takes the main place in achieving through the development of activities. Today's it is a witness that most of the students are not trying to expand their knowledge reserves we will be They do not actively participate in classes. They are free activities outside the educational process are more interested. One of the reasons for this is that when students go to school, teachers and they try to win the love and attention of their classmates. This is the problem the solution of which is one of the most important issues of continuous education, the student coming to school and studying. The level of mastery is important to realize your desire. In the students' group joint achievement, that is, it is faster and more effective during work in small groups. Through the support of his comrades, he gets his place in the group and contributes to the success of his team a sense of inclusion is formed. This motivation is confidence and desire for the next activity, working together creates positive relationships with skills. Creating a learning environment that is conducive to success

for every student is provided through It is his responsibility to satisfy the knowledge needs of the student in the educational situation of experts have been emphasizing that it occupies an important place in the development. If the student is in a learning situation if he is given the chance to succeed, he will be able to choose the right path for himself in life.

The motivational sphere is the basis of personality. Formation of educational motives - manifestation of internal educational motives in the educational institution, understanding of them by students and creation of conditions for personal development of the field of motivation. It is possible and necessary to stimulate its development through special psychological techniques. The general meaning of developing educational motivation is to transfer students from the level of negative and indifferent attitude to learning to mature forms of positive attitude to education - effective, conscious, responsible. At first, a first-grader is interested in the process of educational activity, does not understand its importance. The game has to do more in pronouncing sounds than writing letter elements. When the interest in the results of the educational work appears, the students of the first grade begin to be interested in the content of the educational activity, in gaining knowledge. is a favorable ground for the formation of a responsible attitude. 3rd-4th grade students begin to have a selective attitude to certain academic subjects, as a result of which the general motivation for learning is more differentiated: positive and negative motivation for the educational process depending on the interest in the subject.

Also, motive means the attitude of the student to the performance of his activity can also be understood. Motives are needs and interests, aspirations and emotions, can act in the form of basic concepts and ideals. That's why motives are a very complex structure, analysis of alternatives, choices and decisions is a dynamic system that can be evaluated. Learning motivation didactics and is one of the central problems of pedagogical psychology. This Some progress has been made in this regard, but the problem has yet to be fully resolved not achieved. Due to the changeability, mobility, variety of motives defining their specific structural structure, specific methods and means of management it is difficult to determine.

A number of didactic studies carried out by pedagogic scientists shows that among the teaching factors that increase the effectiveness of the educational process the factor of motivation for educational activity is in the first place, i.e 92% of the effectiveness of education depends on the motivation of educational activities. A person who understands human nature at least a little admits that this is not in vain is enough. Motives are the main driving force of the didactic process. Learning motivations, using

them correctly and directing them correctly acquisition determines the main essence of the content of pedagogical activity. Motivation - (Latin moveo - means to move, move meaning) these students are involved in effective educational and cognitive activities, education processes, methods that lead to active mastering of the content of the material, is a common name for tools. Figuratively speaking, the reins of motivation both the teacher and the students hold it in their hands. Teaching activity from the point of view, from the point of view of educational motivation, study activity if we look at it, we can talk about motivating educational activities. Motivation is a change in a person's mental state and attitudes based on motives as a process.

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